

RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS BASED ON DEEP LEARNING

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Xushbaqov Sherzod,

Student of TUIT FSE,

sherzodking5752@gmail.com

Khamraev Mansur,

Student of TUIT FSE,

mxamrayev888@gmail.com

Bakhtiyorova Mokhiruy

Student of TUIT FSE,

baxtiyorovamohiruy@gmail.com

Annotation: *In this article, we describe deep learning-based recommender systems. First, we introduce deep learning in content-based recommender systems. Then, the details of deep learning-based collaborative filtering recommender systems are provided. Next, we present deep learning-based hybrid recommender systems and deep learning in social network-based recommender systems. Finally, we describe deep learning in contextaware recommender systems.*

Key words: *neural network, content-based recommender systems, collaborative filtering recommender systems, Autoencoder-based collaborative filtering method, Boltzmann machine*

Introduction

Deep learning based recommender systems can be divided into two broad categories: the integration model and the neural network model. Considering whether it integrates traditional deep learning recommendation models or relies solely on deep learning techniques, we split the integration model into two models: integrate deep learning with a traditional recommendation model, and recommend relying solely on a deep learning model. Integrating deep learning with a traditional recommendation model is an attempt to combine deep learning methods with traditional recommendation methods in one way or another. Recommend relying solely on a deep learning model relying on deep learning methods without any form of assistance from traditional recommendation models.

According to the types of deep learning methods used. We divide the neural network model into two categories: models using a single deep learning technique and a deep composite model. The motivation behind the deep composite model is that different deep learning methods can complement each other and provide a more powerful hybrid model. The basic architecture of a deep learning based recommender system as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The architecture of deep learning-based recommender systems

Deep learning in content-based recommender systems

The content-based recommendation system is mainly based on supporting product and user information. A varied range of supporting information such as texts, images and videos can be taken into account. Deep learning in content-based recommender systems is mainly used to efficiently capture non-linear and non-trivial relationships between a user and an element, and to enable the codification of more complex abstractions as representations of data at higher levels. In addition, it captures complex relationships within the data itself from the many available data sources such as contextual, textual, and visual information.

Deep learning in collaborative filtering recommender systems

Collaborative filtering (CF) is a widely used approach in recommender systems to solve many real world problems. Traditional CF-based methods use a user item matrix

that encodes users' individual preferences for learning items to make recommendations. In real applications, the score matrix is usually very sparse, resulting in a significant degradation in the performance of recommendations based on CF methods. Some advanced CF methods use an increasing amount of extra information to solve the problem of data sparseness, as well as the problem of cold start. However, the studied latent factors may not be effective due to the sparse nature of the user element matrix and additional information. Some researchers are leveraging advances in the study of efficient representations in deep learning, proposing deep learning-based collaborative filtering methods, which are a kind of recommendation based collaborative filtering methods based on models.

Autoencoder-based collaborative filtering method

Autoencoder-based Collaborative Filtering (ACF) is the first autoencoder-based collaborative recommendation model. Instead of using the original partial observed vectors, it decomposes them by integer ratings. Sedhain et al. proposed autoencoder-based collaborative filtering recommendation method(AutoRec), the input of model is user-based ratings or item-based ratings in the rating matrix R , produces an output through encoding and decoding process and optimizes the model parameters by minimizing the reconstruction error. For example, if the rating score is integer in the range of, each r_{ui} will be divided into five partial vectors.

Figure 2. AE-based collaborative filtering model

Figure 2 presents an example of AE-based collaborative filtering model, where rating scale from 1 to 5. The blue entries indicate that the user has rated that item as the corresponding rating (e.g. the user gives 5 for item 1, 1 for item 5). The cost function of autoencoder-based collaborative filtering recommendation method aims at reducing the mean squared error. The rating prediction of autoencoder-based collaborative filtering recommendation method is calculated by summarizing each entry of the five vectors, then scaled by the maximum rating K . It uses RBM to pretrain the parameters as well as to avoid local optimum. Stacking several autoencoders together also enhances the accuracy slightly. However, there are two demerits of autoencoder-based collaborative filtering recommendation method: it fails to deal with non-integer ratings; the

decomposition of partial observed vectors increases the sparseness of input data and leads to worse prediction accuracy.

Collaborative Denoising Auto-Encoder (CDAE) is principally used for ranking prediction. The input of CDAE is user partial observed implicit feedback. The entry value is 1 if the user likes the movie, otherwise 0. It can also be regarded as a preference vector which reflects user's interests to items. The input of CDAE is corrupted by Gaussian noise. CDAE initially updates its parameters using SGD over all feedback. However, the authors argued that it is impractical to take all ratings into consideration in real world applications, so they proposed a negative sampling technique to sample a small subset from the negative set (items with which the user has not interacted), which reduces the time complexity substantially without degrading the ranking quality.

Restricted Boltzmann machine based collaborative filtering method

Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) is a two-layer neural network consisting of a visible layer and a hidden layer. It is one of the first artificial neural networks capable of solving complex learning problems by learning the internal expression of data. The efficiency of training is greatly improved as the connection between the same layers is removed. Salakhutdinov et al. proposed a restricted recommender system based on the Boltzmann machine. The researchers also suggested using conditional RBM to include implicit feedback information. The visible unit of RBM is limited to binary values, so the rating score is presented in direct vector to accommodate this limitation. The structure of the model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. RBM-based collaborative filtering model

Every RBM has the same number of hidden units, but an RBM only has visible softmax units for the movies rated by that user, so an RBM has few connections if that user rated few movies. Each RBM only has a single training case, but all of the corresponding weights and biases are tied together, so if two users have rated the same movie, their two RBM's must use the same weights between the softmax visible unit for that movie and the hidden units. The binary states of the hidden units can be quite different for different users. Suppose user rated N movies, the number of visible units is n , Let M be a $X \times N$ matrix where $r_{ui}^x = 1$ if user u rated movie i as x and $r_{ui}^x = 0$ otherwise. Then:

$$p(r_{ui}^x = 1|h) = \frac{\exp(b_i^x + \sum_{j=1}^T h_j w_{ij}^x)}{\sum_{l=1}^X \exp(b_i^l + \sum_{j=1}^T h_j w_{ij}^l)}$$

$$p(h_j = 1|M) = \sigma(b_j + \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^T r_{ui}^x w_{ij}^x)$$

where $\sigma(x) = 1/(1 + e^{-x})$ is the logistic function, w_{ij}^x is a symmetric interaction parameter between hidden unit j and rating x of movie i , b_i^x is the bias of rating x for movie i and b_j is the bias of hidden unit j .

Recurrent neural network-based collaborative filtering method

Recurrent neural network (RNN) is suitable for modelling sequential data. Unlike feedforward neural network, there are loops and memories in RNN to remember former computations. Variants such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) network are often deployed in practice to overcome the vanishing gradient problem. The basic idea of RNN-based collaborative filtering is to use RNN to model the effect of user historical sequence behavior on the user current behavior, then recommends items for the user and predicts user’s behavior. Figure 4 is a basic RNN-based collaborative filtering method framework. Suppose the input is $\{I_1, I_2, \dots, I_t\}$, $O_t = \sigma(g(W \cdot h_{t-1} + V \cdot I_t) \cdot V)$, g is the activation function, O_t is the output, it denotes the probability of selecting a specific item at time t , it is usually calculated by the hidden vector at time t . σ is softmax function. Recent advancements have demonstrated the efficacy of RNN in solving this session-based recommendation.

Figure 4. RNN-based collaborative filtering model

Deep learning-based hybrid recommender systems

Traditional CF-based methods employ the user-item matrix which encodes the individual preferences of users for items for learning to make recommendation. In real applications, the rating matrix is usually very sparse, causing CF-based methods to degrade significantly in recommendation performance. In this case, some improved CF methods utilize the increasing amount of side information to address the data sparsity problem as well as the cold start problem. However, the learned latent factors may not be effective due to the sparse nature of the user-item matrix and the side information. The basic idea of deep learning-based hybrid recommendation method is to combine the content-based recommendation methods with collaborative filtering recommendation methods, integrate the feature learning of the user or item and the process of

recommendation into a unified framework. Some researchers utilize advances of learning effective representations in deep learning, propose a stacked denoising autoencoder-based hybrid model which jointly performs deep users and items' latent factors learning from side information and collaborative filtering from the rating matrix.

An autoencoder is a specific form of neural network, which consists of an encoder and a decoder component. The encoder takes a given input and maps it to a hidden representation, while the decoder maps this hidden representation back to a reconstructed version of input. The parameters of the autoencoder are learned to minimize the reconstruction error, measured by some loss function. However, denoising autoencoders(DAE) incorporate a slight modification to this setup, which reconstructs the input from a corrupted version with the motivation of learning a more effective representation from the input. A denoising autoencoder is trained to reconstruct the original input from its corrupted version by minimizing loss function. Usually, choices of corruption include additive isotropic Gaussian noise or binary masking noise. Moreover, various types of autoencoders have been developed in several domains to show promising results.

Stacked denoising autoencoder-based hybrid recommendation model makes use of both rating matrix and side information and combines SDAE and matrix factorization together. Matrix factorization is a widely used model-based CF method with excellent scalability and accuracy, and SDAE is a powerful way to extract high-level representations from raw inputs. The combination of these two models leverages their benefits for learning more expressive models. The model contains three components: the upper component and the lower component are two SDAEs which extract latent factor vectors for users and items respectively; the middle component decomposes the rating matrix \mathbf{R} into two latent factor matrices. The basic architecture of stacked denoising autoencoder-based hybrid recommendation method is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The architecture of stacked denoising autoencoder -based hybrid recommendation method

Given the user-item rating matrix \mathbf{R} , we first transform \mathbf{R} into the set $S^{(u)}$ containing m instances $\{S_1^{(u)}, \dots, S_m^{(u)}\}$, where $S_i^{(u)} = \{R_{i1}, \dots, R_{in}\}$ is the n -dimensional feedback vector of user i on all the items. Similarly, we can obtain set $S^{(i)}$ with n instances $\{S_1^{(i)}, \dots, S_n^{(i)}\}$, where $S_i^{(i)} = \{R_{i1}, \dots, R_{im}\}$ is the m -dimensional feedback vector of item j rated by all the users. Hybrid model learns user and item latent factors (i.e., \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V}) from \mathbf{R} , $S^{(u)}$, $S^{(i)}$ and the additional side information (i.e., \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y}) through the following optimization objective:

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}} G(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{V}) + \alpha (||\mathbf{U}||_F^2 + ||\mathbf{V}||_F^2) + \beta \sigma(S^{(u)}, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{U}) + \gamma \sigma(S^{(i)}, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{V})$$

where $\sigma(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the function that connects the user or item side information with the latent factors, $G(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the loss function for decomposing the rating matrix \mathbf{R} into two latent factor matrices \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} , α is a regularization parameter, β and γ are the trade-off parameters. Note that, the last two terms in Equation (2) devised using SDAE model which extracts latent factor matrix from the rating matrix and additional side information.

Explainability of deep learning based recommender system

Deep learning-based recommender systems use the deep learning model to directly predict the user preferences by using multi-source heterogeneous data. The result of the model training is to get the weights between the neurons of deep neural network. It is

difficult to give a reasonable explanation directly to the recommendation results. So, making explainable recommendations seem to be impossible. One way is to make explainable predictions to users, allowing them to understand the factors behind the network's recommendations, display an appropriate recommendation reason to tell the user why the system considers such a recommendation to be reasonable. The other way is to focus on explain-ability to the practitioner, probing weights and activations to understand more about the model. Therefore, it is also another possible research direction of deep learning-based recommender system, and next step would be to design better deep learningbased recommender models to provide conversational or generative explanations.

Conclusion

The dramatic increase in the amount of data being produced by electronic and automated devices necessitates the need for intelligent techniques and applications that can properly and intelligently store, process, access and analyze information for maximum benefits to users. Deep learning-based recommender systems(DLRS) are of such leading solutions to these challenges, which are appropriate tools to quickly aid the process of information seeking. Deep learning-based recommender systems can learn the latent representations of users and items from massive data, and then construct a recommendation model, finally generate an effective recommendation list for the user. The main tasks of the deep learning-based recommender systems are how to organize the massive multi-source heterogeneous data, build more suitable user models according to user preferences requirements, and improve the performance and user satisfaction.

Compared with traditional recommender systems, deep learning-based recommender systems can use deep learning technique to automatically learn the latent features of user and item by integrating various types of multi-source heterogeneous data, model the sequence patterns of user behavior, more effectively reflect the user's different preferences and improve the accuracy of recommendation. It is hoped that this review will assist novice and new researchers to understand the development of DLRS. Moreover, expert researchers can use this review as a benchmark to develop DLRS and as a reference to the limitations of DLRS.

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